

BARRIERS TO THE SOCIAL ENTERPRISE PERFORMANCE: A LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Gururaja B.L, Dr. Nagaraja B¹

Assistant Professor, School of Arts Humanities and Commerce, Department of Commerce and Management, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Mysuru Campus

Abstract: Social entrepreneurs are essential in addressing social problems and pursuing long-term commercial strategies. However, several barriers often hinder their ability to have a major impact, which negatively affects their performance. The current study offers a systematic examination of the barriers to social enterprise success, using knowledge from a range of sources from the Scopus and Google Scholar databases. The literature includes policy papers, practitioner experiences, and scholarly research. The evaluation includes typical barriers such as legal restrictions, budgetary limitations, market difficulties, skills shortages, infrastructural shortcomings, and cultural considerations. This review attempts to offer an in-depth analysis of the challenges encountered by social enterprises globally by synthesizing the current research. The insight obtained from this research can help practitioners, investors, and policymakers in creating specific interventions and support systems to get through such barriers and foster an enabling environment for social enterprise development.

Keywords: Social Enterprise, Barriers, Performance

JEL Classification Number: M10, M12

Introduction

Social entrepreneurship plays a significant role in many countries to fill the gaps in social services. It fosters to provide employment generation and solves social problems, which helps in the economic development of a country (Wang et al., 2016; Mikołajczak, 2021). Social entrepreneurship has emerged as a dynamic force for addressing complex societal challenges while simultaneously pursuing financial sustainability (Bhattarai et al., 2019; Di Domenico, Haugh, & Tracey, 2010). These ventures operate at the intersection of business acumen and social impact, striving to create positive change by harnessing market mechanisms. However, despite their noble intentions and innovative approaches, social enterprises often encounter various barriers that impede their performance and inhibit their ability to achieve their full potential.

Understanding the barriers to social enterprise performance is crucial for stakeholders ranging from entrepreneurs and investors to policymakers and researchers. Extant studies have documented the various barriers to social enterprise performance (Iskandar et al., 2022; Davies et al., 2018; Cosa & Urban, 2023; Robinson, 2006; Austin et al., 2006; Dey & Teasdale, 2016; Teasdale, 2012; Dees & Anderson, 2022). While the literature has made considerable efforts to explain and describe the idea, major gaps remain in our knowledge of its potential and the conditions that promote or inhibit development. The effectiveness of social enterprises in accomplishing economic goals has lately become a hot topic, with researchers looking into how they might enhance market-based revenues and the influence of those revenues on attaining social goals (Mason & Doherty, 2016). Much of this discussion, however, has focused on higher-income regions, with middle- and low-income nations severely underrepresented in the literature (Littlewood & Holt, 2018; Karanda & Toledano, 2012). Hence, the study aims to examine and clarify the many obstacles that social entrepreneurs must overcome to achieve both financial sustainability and social impact in the world. Based on an extensive analysis of previous research, factual data, and the study aims to clarify the wide range of difficulties encountered by social entrepreneurs working in different industries and contexts. The goal of the study is to gain a deeper knowledge of the complex factors influencing the success of social enterprise by critically analysing these barriers and identifying workable solutions.

Theoretical Background

“Social entrepreneurship, commonly defined as “entrepreneurial activity with an embedded social purpose” (Austin et al., 2006 p 32). Social entrepreneurship involves identifying, evaluating, and exploiting opportunities that create social value. Entrepreneurs detect supply or demand for value-creating products or services, understanding social needs, and fulfilling them through creative organization. This focus on social value is consistent across various definitions (Certo & Miller, 2008).

¹ *Corresponding Author: Assistant Professor, School of Commerce and Management, Department of Commerce, Garden City University, Bengaluru*

The institutional environment hypothesis is applicable to this investigation (North, 2017). Within the field of institutional economics, the theory of institutional economics is well-known. The larger theoretical framework of institutional economics makes the premise that various rules governing organisations and human behaviour in social interactions control the institutional environment (North, 2017). According to North (2017), cultural, social, and political institutions are the three categories of institutions that control the behaviour of social actors. Furthermore, North (2017) distinguishes between official and informal institutions. While self-imposed ethics, socially accepted norms, and behaviours make up informal institutions, formal institutions include laws, constitutions, and regulations. In his comprehensive description of these institutions, Pacut (2020) points out that formal institutions are those that were founded by law, while social rules design informal institutions, which are transmitted, evolutionary, and enforced outside the law by society. North (2017) states that institutions are an essential component within the discipline of institutional economics because they are the rules of actions and affect individuals' actions and groups. Therefore, the interaction between the agents within an institutional construct produces a far-reaching impact (North, 2017).

Literature Review

Several studies have documented the barriers to social enterprise performance all over the world. The relevant literature is presented in the section. Extant studies have identified various barriers for social enterprise performance in the globe. Pande's (2021) study explores factors motivating social entrepreneurs, revealing financial and social obstacles. Barriers to social entrepreneurship development in the Czech Republic, focusing on the community of practice on inclusive entrepreneurship methodology. It highlights limited financial support options and lack of interest from banks in improving loan availability (Pelucha et al., 2017). Financial debt negatively affects the return on capital employed component of performance of social enterprises (Tirumalsety & Gurtoo, 2019). Sourcing financing, staff retention, and measuring business scale are the barriers for social enterprises (Hynes, 2009).

Among Malaysian research universities using Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour found that students face barriers such as lack of competency, self-confidence, and resources (Shahverdi et al., 2018). Research on social enterprise in the construction sector in UK is facing significant barriers due to ignorance, mistrust, and resistance (Worrall et al., 2010). Kusyik & Lozano (2007) the study used a thematic analysis from 1973 to 2006 found that 80 drivers and 96 barriers to high social performance are identified. A secondary based study found that lack of cohesive knowledge is the barrier for social enterprise performance (Lee et al., 2014).

Methodology of the Study

'According to (Butler et al., 2016), the initial step in a systematic literature review is to identify the review's goal derived from the research question' (Iskandar et al., 2022). Therefore, this research aims to identify barriers to social enterprise performance. Charrois (2015) 'advises that a researcher should use at least two databases in a systematic review'. Two databases such as the Scopus and Google Scholar were selected for the literature search in the present study. Keywords including "social enterprise," "performance," "barriers," "challenges," and variations thereof were used in different combinations to retrieve relevant literature. Around 110 literatures were extracted from the databases. Duplication and studies which are not related to the study, non-English articles, grey literature, and studies lacking relevance to the topic were excluded. Around 37 literature was selected based on inclusion criteria. All articles included in field, articles published between 2010 and 2020, articles in English language, only full text articles were considered for inclusion criteria for the study. There is no geographical boundary to the article selected for the study. Identified literature was screened based on relevance to the research topic. Articles focusing on barriers to social enterprise performance, either broadly or within specific contexts, were selected for detailed review. Studies presenting empirical evidence, theoretical frameworks, conceptual discussions, or case studies related to barriers faced by social enterprises were included.

Barriers to Social Enterprise Performance

'Social enterprises operate under highly competitive resource mobilization conditions. Barriers in this area faced by social enterprises can be considered at the endogenous and exogenous levels' ((Zhang & Baum, 2004 p15). Some researchers define them as internal and external challenges.

External Barriers

The most common external barriers faced by social enterprises are legal structures and challenges in operating under the current legal system. Legislative issues and bureaucracy are the most significant, with non-governmental organization laws being particularly burdensome. Working between these laws and traditional businesses is particularly difficult. Most Social enterprises register as NGOs, associations, or companies, with some having both. The legal framework changes, and operating as an NGO restricts market-based revenues. There is no middle ground between for-profit and non-profit registration, making it difficult to generate income and use it for a mission (Ismail & Johnson, 2019). Indonesian enterprises, accounting for 54% of all enterprises, have significant potential due to their socially disadvantaged status. Historically, Indonesia's political climate has been unfavourable, leading to the discouragement of civic societies. However, over time, civil society has been encouraged to improve livelihoods. Local groups, local administrations, and international NGOs have aggressively addressed local concerns, demonstrating the country's potential for growth (Rahman, 2015).

Lack of finance is one of the barriers. This lack of flexibility in funding mechanisms is a significant obstacle for social entrepreneurs. The majority of participants have not received any loans or social investments, suggesting a gap in access to funding mechanisms for organizational growth and flexibility (Ismail & Johnson, 2019). The same findings found in Czech Republic, faces challenges in the development of social enterprises due to limited financial support options. Slovakia, Hungary, and Poland all have limited financial support systems. Slovakia receives state funding, EU funds, NESsT, tax assignment, Erste bank, and Provida Foundation. Hungary's financial support comes from NESsT and the government through EU funds. Poland may obtain funds from European funds, but there are two commercial funds for loans. Most funding is based on EU financial sources. These barriers hinder the growth of SEs in these countries (EC, 2014; Pelucha et al., 2017).

Economy

The economic system also plays an important role in the growth of social enterprises in a country. The Asian Development Bank (2015) found that the Indonesian economy is experiencing turbulence, causing poor performance for businesses and social enterprises. This has led to a deterioration in livelihoods like agriculture and fishing, causing social problems Pratono & Sutanti (2016) reported that despite being the largest territory and holding the highest population in Southeast Asia, industries like fishing and agriculture are underperforming. However, local communities are experiencing these issues, providing opportunities for social enterprises to provide necessary support. The economy's dual property nature creates both opportunities and limitations for businesses, making it a complex theme that can both benefit and hinder social organizations (Iskandar et al., 2022). Despite being the largest country in Southeast Asia in terms of size and people, the country's sectors, including agriculture and fisheries, are among the lowest performing, according to Pratono and Sutanti (2016). Quincieu (2015) also draws attention to the problem's result and points out that poverty is pervasive in Indonesia's agriculture industry. Quincieu (2015) makes a good point since it is reasonable to assume that people will live well given the abundance of resources Pratono and Sutanti (2016) mentioned above. Due to the issue, as was previously noted, around 66% of Indonesians' wages, particularly those of lower income levels, are spent on food (Pratono & Sutanti, 2016). As a result, poverty may be considered one of the social objectives of social enterprises could pursue once the economy stabilizes.

Politics

Politics is one of the barriers to social enterprises. Politics is a significant barrier in institutional theory, as it influences socio-cultural and economic factors. (Al-Hyari et al., 2011; Irjayanti & Azis, 2012; Nix Stevenson, 2013; Pratono & Sutanti, 2016; Rahman, 2015). Politics is a significant barrier in institutional theory, as it influences socio-cultural and economic factors. Political policies affect a country's economic outcomes and business outcomes due to the legal framework arising from political processes. Indonesia has experienced political instability due to dictatorial leadership, which hinders economic growth and business outcomes.

Internal Barriers

A study on internal organizational barriers revealed three main categories: organizational capacity, team knowledge and skills, and investment readiness. Participants emphasized challenges with organizational capacity, such as assuming adequate-sized teams and full-time staff. Social enterprises struggle with funding and lack business skills, hindering the hiring of qualified staff. Only 3 out of 22 organizations had more than 25% full-time staff, with 59% having part-time staff. 80% engaged in some level of volunteer, indicating understaffing and limited capacity to achieve specific aims (Ismail & Johnson, 2019). Robinson (2006) identifies various barriers to business penetration, including economic, social, institutional, and cultural, that hinder social entrepreneurs from seizing market opportunities (Iskandar et al., 2022; Davies et al., 2018).

Cultural barriers are also one of the problems in Indonesia. therefore, culture has a moderating role in business. The unwritten or informal cultural code emphasizes relationships over commerce. This unwritten or

informal rule may have a detrimental influence on business growth, particularly for foreigners who start social businesses owing to a lack of information or narrow social networks (Iskandar et al., 2022). The current literature study also demonstrated how, within an institutional theoretical framework, culture functions as a moderating component. According to Cole (2007) and Emerhub (2017), Indonesians have a high-power distance culture and respect authority. The importance Indonesians place on relationships over business is another aspect of their culture that might have an impact on social enterprise success. According to a 2017 Emerhub article, Indonesians appreciate social interaction and try to get to know the individuals they would be doing business with. The results suggested that culture was a complex institution. Adeney-Risakotta (2014), for example, states that religion—Islam being the predominant faith—plays a significant role in Indonesian culture. People are therefore probably going to be in tighter ties with one another. Therefore, this factor acts as a barrier to social enterprises' performance because a person from outside Indonesia might have difficulty establishing the said relationships.

In the Czech Republic and other countries, social enterprises face challenges due to insufficient knowledge, skills, and experience of start-ups. This leads to frustration and low motivation for further entrepreneurship. Social enterprises in the Czech Republic and Slovakia are undeveloped, with no networks or platforms for sharing experiences (EC 2014). There is also a lack of an attractive flexible professional education system for better functioning of SEs. Pcolinska (2014) states that, in Hungary, the lack of awareness and understanding of SEs and the absence of a long-term government concept are main barriers. In Poland, the main barriers include the absence of entrepreneurial skills and lack of support for existing SEs. More effective education in SE is needed, but mental changes related to perception of social enterprises are needed (Majercikova, 2015).

Result and Discussion

Lack of Access to Capital

One of the most cited barriers to social enterprise performance is the limited access to capital. Social enterprises often struggle to secure funding due to their hybrid nature, which makes them less attractive to traditional investors. Studies have highlighted the challenges social enterprises face in accessing both debt and equity financing, particularly from mainstream financial institutions that prioritize profit-maximizing ventures.

Regulatory and Legal Constraints

Regulatory and legal barriers pose significant challenges to social enterprises, particularly in terms of legal structures, taxation, and compliance requirements. Complex regulations and ambiguities in legal frameworks often deter potential investors and hinder the growth and sustainability of social enterprises.

Market Challenges

Social enterprises operate in dynamic and often competitive markets, facing challenges such as limited market demand, pricing pressures, and competition from traditional businesses. Lack of consumer awareness and understanding of social enterprise products or services can also impede market penetration and growth.

Limited Management Capacity:

Many social enterprises struggle with limited management capacity, including inadequate leadership skills, organizational structures, and human resource management practices. Many social enterprises struggle with limited management capacity, including inadequate leadership skills, organizational structures, and human resource management practices.

Mitigation of barriers of social enterprise performance

Social enterprises must actively implement mitigation approaches to ensure their ability to operate effectively. Extant studies have shown that strategic orientation is crucial for market effectiveness and customer satisfaction in both social and commercial aspects of the enterprise. To navigate their complex, pluralist institutional environment, social enterprises can harness, and channel multiple forces embedded in their environment, such as formal and informal networks. Systematic business planning can attract investment and funding to help mitigate financial challenges (Liu et al., 2014; Wolf & Mair, 2019). Managing internal and external tensions is essential for social enterprises and embracing rather than resolving challenges can provide an effective pathway to success. Temporal and geographic resolution strategies can also help mitigate paradox issues by integrating collaborative and cooperative approaches. Hybridized venture collaboration can also help mitigate inherent tensions that act as barriers to success (Barraket et al., 2016; Gillett et al., 2019). Networking can help address isolation and resource challenges by building collaborative, mutually beneficial relationships with key stakeholders. Successful hybrid business models require suitable strategies and partnerships to reduce institutional and stakeholder complexity (Abedin et al., 2021). Countries could introduce a social enterprise-oriented

policy to help social enterprises overcome legal barriers, culture, and government bureaucracy, enhance capital access, and guarantee democratic participation. Supporting local social entrepreneurship is crucial for its success, as suggested by Mendell (2010). Kolakovic (2018) highlighted the importance of financial support frameworks for social enterprises, as economic turmoil can negatively impact them due to capital constraints, a strategy that has proven successful in many countries.

Conclusion

The literature review on barriers to social enterprise performance highlights the complexities faced by these enterprises in their pursuit of social and economic impact. Key barriers include internal and external barriers. These challenges hinder social enterprises' ability to demonstrate their impact effectively, access capital, navigate restrictive financial environments, and adapt to complex legal frameworks and bureaucratic procedures. Context-specific challenges, such as geographical location, cultural norms, and political climates, also shape the operating environment for social enterprises, necessitating tailored strategies and adaptive approaches. Despite these challenges, social enterprises demonstrate resilience and ingenuity in devising innovative solutions and collaborative strategies to address barriers and enhance performance. The literature review emphasizes the need for a holistic understanding of barriers to social enterprise performance, recognizing the interplay of internal and external factors shaping organizational dynamics. Addressing these barriers through targeted interventions, collaborative partnerships, and supportive ecosystems can foster an enabling environment conducive to sustainable growth and impact, advancing their contributions to social and economic development.

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